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2 **Modified-Thermal Borehole Shear Test Device and Testing Procedure to Investigate the**
3 **Soil-Structure Interaction of Energy Piles**
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37 **Submitted to**
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1 **INTRODUCTION**

2 The use of geothermal deep foundations (energy piles) has been rapidly increasing in Europe, Japan,
3 and China to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Brandl 2006; Laloui et al. 2006; Ooka et al. 2007;
4 and Gao et al. 2008). When compared to conventional geothermal boreholes, energy piles (with
5 embedded polyethylene pipe heat exchangers connected to a ground source heat pump) are part of
6 the structure and require no additional drilling cost. However, the intermittent operation of the heat
7 pump, which depends on heating and cooling loads of the building, introduces new challenges to
8 the foundation design due to subjecting it and the surrounding soil to daily and seasonal temperature
9 changes and cycles.

10

11 Temperature change and cycles alter soil properties and lead to expansion and contraction of the
12 pile in the axial and radial directions, both of which affect the soil-pile interaction of axially loaded
13 foundations (Amatya et al. 2012; Bourne-Webb et al., 2009). Extensive experimental tests have
14 been performed by researchers to investigate the behaviors of soils subjected to temperature
15 changes (e.g., Campanella and Mitchell 1968; Laguros 1969; Noble and Demirel 1969; Houston et
16 al. 1985; Kuntiwattanakul et al. 1995; Cekerevac and Laloui 2004); however, limited investigations
17 focused on evaluating the effects of temperature cycles (TC) on soil properties (e.g., Burghignoli
18 et al. 2000; Mašin and Khalili 2012). Temperature changes and cycles also induce axial and radial
19 expansion and contraction of the pile altering the interaction along the soil-pile interface (Saggu
20 and Chakraborty 2015). Researches have investigated the effects of pile axial expansion and
21 contraction (considering the end-restraint) on shear stresses at the soil-pile interface and on axial
22 stresses in the pile (e.g., Brandl 2006; Laloui et al. 2006, Bourne-Webb et al. 2009; McCartney and
23 Murphy 2012; Suryatriyastuti et al. 2012, Olgun et al. 2014, etc.). However, the effects of
24 thermally-induced radial expansion and contraction on the soil-foundation interaction for energy

1 piles have not been fully investigated. Attempts to measure the effects of the operation of energy
2 pile systems on the soil-pile interaction and interface properties have been focusing on the effects
3 of temperature changes only. Examples of these investigations include performing modified direct
4 shear tests by Xiao et al. (2014 and 2017); Di Donna et al. (2015); and Yavari et al. (2016). A
5 modified Borehole Shear Test (m-BST) device was also used to examine this effect by Suleiman
6 and Xiao (2014) and Murphy and McCartney (2014). The thermal-BST (TBST) performed by
7 Murphy and McCartney (2014) only considered temperature changes. Suleiman and Xiao (2014)
8 presented preliminary design and results of a manually-controlled TBST which simulated
9 temperature change and radial expansion, but not accurately simulating the effects of temperature
10 and radial displacement cycles (RDC). In this present paper, a new fully-automated modified-
11 thermal BST (Modified-TBST) device that is capable of simulating temperature changes and cycles
12 as well as radial expansion and contraction displacements and cycles, is described. This paper
13 focuses on detailed description of the device, its capabilities and limitations, and a recommended
14 testing control and procedure. Furthermore, preliminary results of shear stress vs. displacement
15 relationships (t-z curves) are presented.

16

17 **BACKGROUND**

18 **Operation of Energy Piles**

19 The thermal and mechanical responses of energy piles used as structural support members and heat
20 exchangers have been documented in several case histories (e.g., Laloui et al. 2006; Ooka et al.
21 2007; Hamada et al. 2007; Adam and Markiewicz 2009; Bourne-Webb et al. 2009; Wood et al.
22 2009; Amatya et al. 2012; Murphy and McCartney 2015). Energy piles are commonly constructed
23 with diameters ranging from 0.3 to 1.5 m, lengths of 10 to 30 m and with heat exchangers made of
24 polyethylene pipe (Laloui and Di Donna 2013). The net thermal output of energy piles ranges from

1 18 to 120 W per meter of the foundation length and the system typically provides 3 to 5 energy
2 units for each unit consumed in operation (Preene and Powrie 2009; Bourne-Webb 2013).

3 The heat pump connected to energy piles operates in cycles (intermittent operation), in which it
4 functions for a period of time (running time) then stops for another period (stoppage time). The
5 data reported by Amis (2011) indicates that in the U.K., the running time during summer and winter
6 ranges from 8 to 16 hours followed by a stoppage time ranging from 1 to 3 hours. During the
7 month of March, Wood et al. (2009) reported that the typical daily cycle of a heat pump in the U.K.
8 consists of 1.5 hours running time and 30 minutes stoppage time. Similarly, Brandl (2006) reported
9 a running time in the range of 8 to 20 hours during summer in Austria. In Spain, Montagud et al.
10 (2011) reported a running time of 35 minutes for a typical cooling day (summer) and 30 minutes
11 for a typical heating day (winter). These heat pump running and stoppage times (intermittent
12 operation) can be critical for the response of axially loaded energy piles. These running and
13 stoppage times of the heat pump result in heating and cooling cycles of the pile and surrounding
14 soil altering soil properties, effective stresses, and soil-pile interaction, which have not been fully
15 investigated.

16

17 The temperature distributions within energy piles and surrounding soils have been investigated by
18 several researchers in different countries (e.g., U.S., Europe, Japan, and China) (Brandl 2006;
19 Hamada et al. 2007; Wood et al. 2009; Bourne-Webb et al. 2009; Amis 2011; Abdelaziz et al. 2011;
20 Shang et al. 2011; Akrouch et al. 2013; Murphy and McCartney 2015; Batini et al. 2015;
21 Loveridge et al. 2016). The temperature change of the pile depends on the heating or cooling loads.
22 Based on the data presented in these references, the following is concluded: (1) the common in-
23 operation temperature of energy piles range from -1 to 35°C; (2) the temperature difference
24 between the pile and the soil is approximately 1 to 2°C, which means that the soil temperature

1 ranges from 1 to 33°C and may rise up to 40°C in cooling-dominated environments, extreme
2 climate conditions, or when the energy piles function as solar energy storage sinks according to
3 Gabrielsson et al. (2000); (3) the daily temperature changes of energy piles range from 4 to 8 °C
4 (Amis 2011; Batini et al. 2015); (4) the temperature changes throughout a whole year (maximum
5 difference between lowest and highest pile temperature) was approximately 20 °C (Murphy and
6 McCartney 2015; Loveridge et al. 2016); and (5) energy piles alter the soil temperature along most
7 of the total length of the pile. If the intermittent operation (temperature change and cycles) of energy
8 piles affect the soil properties and lead to expansion and contraction of the pile, soil-pile interaction
9 along the interface will be affected. This has been confirmed by field tests and monitoring of
10 energy piles. For example, Amatya et al. (2012) reported that the mobilized shear resistance (per
11 degree change of temperature), which is calculated using axial strain gauge readings under constant
12 mechanical loading, during heating is 1.9 times of that during cooling. In addition, Wang et al.
13 (2015) reported 14% increase in shaft resistance during heating compared to the case with no
14 temperature change; however, Wang et al (2015) did not evaluate the effects of cooling on shaft
15 resistance. Furthermore, analytical study performed by Suryatriyastuti et al. (2012) showed that a
16 temperature change of 15 °C in energy piles result in 21% increase of the normal force on the soil-
17 pile interface during heating and 14% to 65% reduction of the normal force during cooling.

18

19 **Soil-structure Interaction of Axially Loaded Energy Piles**

20 When an energy pile is heated, it expands in both axial and radial directions, and the pile contracts
21 when it is cooled affecting the shear resistance at the soil-pile interface. The thermal-induced
22 expansion and contraction (or deformation) depends on the load and restraint on the top, toe
23 resistance, and surrounding soil properties. The axial deformation effects were well described by
24 Bourne-Webb et al. (2009) and Amatya et al. (2012) for thermal and mechanical loading conditions.
25 For the effects of radial expansion and contraction, Figure 1a shows a pile with soil horizontal

1 (radial) stress distribution normal to the soil-pile interface along the pile with no temperature effects.
2 When subjected to heating, the pile expands radially (horizontally) and the soil reaction (horizontal
3 stress normal to the soil-pile interface) increases, generating larger shear resistance (Figure 1b).
4 When subjected to cooling; however, the pile contracts and the soil reaction decreases leading to a
5 reduction of the shear resistance of the soil-pile interface (Figure 1c). With the heat pump running
6 and stoppage cycles described above (intermittent operation), the soil and the pile are subjected to
7 cycles of temperature change and expansion and contraction, the effects of which on soil-pile
8 interface properties have not been directly measured, which are explored using the Modified-TBST
9 in this paper.

10

11 Using modified direct shear and modified borehole shear tests, the effects of temperature changes
12 on soil-pile interface properties have been investigated by several researchers including Xiao et al.
13 (2014); Suleiman and Xiao (2014); Murphy and McCartney (2014); Di Donna et al. (2015); and
14 Yavari et al. (2016). Direct shear test results reported by Di Donna et al. (2015) showed an increase
15 of the shear resistance of the soil-concrete interface (for saturated clay) when subjected to heating
16 (temperature change only), which may be attributed to water migration away from the interface
17 (thermal consolidation). The results reported by Xiao et al. (2014) and Yavari et al. (2016) showed
18 small temperature effects (for both heating and cooling temperature changes but no cycles) on the
19 friction angle and cohesion of the soil-concrete interface for both saturated clay and unsaturated
20 silt soil conditions. Using a thermal borehole shear test (TBST), Murphy and McCartney (2014)
21 also reported very small effects of temperature (heating and cooling with no temperature cycles)
22 on the friction angle, cohesion and shear resistance of unsaturated soil-concrete interface. Suleiman
23 and Xiao (2014), who conducted preliminary tests using manually-controlled TBST combining the
24 effects of radial displacement and temperature change (with no cycles), showed an increase of the
25 soil-concrete interface shear resistance during heating and expansion, and significant reduction

1 after cooling and contraction. The design of this TBST device described by Suleiman and Xiao
2 (2014) did not allow for easy control and application of temperature changes and cycles combined
3 with simulated thermally-induced radial expansion and contraction and the device described by
4 Murphy and McCartney (2014) did not allow for the application and control of thermally-induced
5 expansion and contraction.

6

7 **Borehole Shear Test Devices**

8 *Conventional Borehole Shear Test (BST)*

9 The conventional borehole shear device (BST) developed by Handy and Fox (1967) was used to
10 measure shear strength properties of soils by performing a direct shear test in situ. The BST consists
11 of a bi-lateral expandable shear head with grooved steel plates. The shear head is lowered into an
12 open borehole, such as the one created by a hollow stem auger. A constant pressure normal to the
13 surface of the borehole is applied by the shear head for typically 5 to 20 minutes to allow for
14 dissipation of any excess pore water pressure after the application of the normal pressure
15 (Lutenegger et al. 1978, Lutenegger and Tierney 1986). When sufficient consolidation time has
16 elapsed, the soil is sheared typically at a displacement rate of 0.05 mm/s by manually applying an
17 upward pulling force, and the shear stress is measured by a dynamometer gauge. In the
18 conventional BST, only the maximum shear stress is recorded (AbdelSalam et al., 2012). The BST
19 is usually conducted three to four times at approximately the same depth using different normal
20 pressures to produce a Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope (Handy and Fox 1967; Handy 1986).

21

22 Several modifications have been introduced to enhance the capability and accuracy of the
23 conventional BST and to overcome certain difficulties during soil testing (Lutenegger et al. 1978;

1 Demartinecourt and Bauer, 1983; Lutenegger and Tierney 1986; Lutenegger and Powell 2008,).

2 These modifications include adding pore water pressure sensors and /or load transducer.

3

4

5 ***Modifications of BST to Measure Interface Properties***

6 BST equipment was also modified to directly measure the shear stress-displacement response (t-z
7 curves) at the soil-pile interface for vertically loaded conventional steel piles (Suleiman et al. 2011;
8 AbdelSalam et al. 2012). The grooved steel plates were replaced by smooth steel plates in a
9 modified-BST device developed by Suleiman et al. (2011) and AbdelSalam et al. (2012) to measure
10 the t-z curves of the interface between a steel pile and surrounding soil. To simulate the soil-pile
11 interaction of energy piles, Suleiman and Xiao (2014) introduced preliminary modifications of BST
12 with manual displacement control to measure the combined effects of temperature and radial
13 displacement on soil-pile interface at temperatures of 2 to 40 °C in the laboratory, and the
14 equipment was called Thermal-BST (TBST). Murphy and McCartney (2014) developed a similar
15 device that can only measure the effects of temperature, and performed tests in Boulder clay and
16 silty sand considering temperature effects ranging from 10 to 45 °C. In the paper described herein,
17 a Modified-Thermal Borehole Shear Test (Modified-TBST) device that is fully-automated and
18 capable of simulating both temperature change and cycles as well as radial expansion/contraction
19 displacements and cycles of energy piles, is described to directly measure the t-z curves at the soil-
20 pile interface. This paper focuses on detailed description of the device, its capabilities and
21 limitations, testing procedure, and presenting preliminary results.

22

23 **DESIGN AND SETUP OF MODIFIED-TBST**

24 **Overview**

1 As shown in Figure 2, the Modified-Thermal Borehole Shear Test (Modified-TBST) system
2 includes a loading frame to apply pulling vertical force on the shear head using a stepper motor.
3 The shear head, which is connected with the loading frame using steel rods, consists of two concrete
4 plates with embedded aluminum tubes for heating and cooling (Figure 3). Two linear
5 potentiometers (displacement gauges) were mounted between the shear plates to measure and
6 control the horizontal displacement simulating the radial expansion and contraction of energy piles.

7 A data acquisition system was used to record the readings of pulling force, vertical displacement
8 of the shear head, and air pressure of the pneumatic piston applying horizontal pressure normal to
9 the soil-concrete interface (σ_h). The system also includes a unit to control the normal pressure on
10 soil-concrete interface. Two refrigerated/heated circulating baths, connected to the aluminum tubes
11 embedded in the concrete plates, were used to apply temperature change and cycles (heating and
12 cooling) simulating the field intermittent operation of heat pumps connected to energy piles. In
13 addition, thermocouples were installed in the soil and on the surface of the concrete shear plates to
14 measure temperature. In total, eighteen thermocouples were used in the soil at three different depths
15 as shown in Figure 2. A tensiometer was also installed in the soil (~5 mm from the interface) to
16 monitor changes of pore pressure.

17

18 Modified-TBSTs were performed in a soil tank filled with compacted soil. The tank was covered
19 by a lid functioning as reaction to apply overburden pressure (p) on the top surface of the soil. An
20 open hole at the center of the lid allows placing the shear head into the borehole. To reduce
21 frictional forces, the inside surface of the tank was covered with a friction-reducing tarp comprised
22 of two thin layers of graphite grease, sandwiched within three layers of thin polyethylene films.
23 Furthermore, tactilus pressure sensors were installed on the inside surface of the tank to evaluate
24 boundary conditions.

1

2 **Design of the Shear Head**

3 The shear head of the Modified-TBST includes two concrete shearing plates with a pneumatic
4 piston in between as shown in Figure 2 and 3a. Increasing the air pressure of the piston pushes the
5 shear plates toward the soil applying different normal pressures (σ_h) on the soil-concrete interface.
6 Two displacement sensors with resolution of 1 μm were fixed between the two shearing plates to
7 measure and control the horizontal displacement (radial displacement). The contact area between
8 a concrete plate and surrounding soil is 52 cm². The concrete plates were casted on high strength
9 stainless steel plates with thickness of 1.2 mm, and U-shaped aluminum heat exchange pipes, with
10 a diameter of 6 mm, were glued on the steel plates as shown in Figure 3b, c and d. The heat
11 exchange pipes were connected with circulating pipes outside of the concrete shearing plates and
12 to the two circulating paths to control the temperature. Insulation was used around the circulating
13 pipes to reduce heat loss and minimize condensation and temperature effects on the soil above the
14 concrete plates (Figure 3e).

15

16 **Loading System**

17 An electric worm-gear pulling system, previously used in the manually operated BST device, was
18 coupled with a stepper motor to pull the shear head upward. However, the friction of the worm gear
19 requires a motor with a higher power and also influences the shearing rate. Therefore, a new loading
20 frame was built using four aluminum T-slotted framings and two steel plates (see Figure 2). The T-
21 slotted framings are standing on a 305 by 356 mm aluminum plate with thickness of 19 mm. The
22 stepper motor was placed on a 305 by 305 mm steel plate, the elevation of which is adjustable along
23 the T-slotted framing using end-feed fasteners. The stepper motor, which has a pulling capacity of
24 2200 N, was connected to the control system to target a vertical displacement rate (shearing rating)
25 of 0.05 mm/s during the shearing stage (applying pulling force on the shear head), which is similar

1 to the rate used in the conventional BST. An S-beam load cell with 2200 N capacity was used to
2 measure the pulling force. Three LVDTs were mounted on the pulling rod to measure the vertical
3 displacement of the shear head during shearing to minimize any tilting effect on measured
4 displacements.

5

6

7 **Heating and Cooling System**

8 Two refrigerated/heated circulating baths were used to simulate temperature changes. One
9 circulating bath was used for heating the soil-concrete interface to the target temperature, while the
10 other was used for cooling. The heating and cooling baths had liquid reservoirs of 8 and 28 liters,
11 respectively, and a mixture of 50% distilled water and 50% glycol was used. The working
12 temperature of the liquid ranges from -30°C to +200°C.

13

14 **Control System**

15 The shear head radial expansion and contraction displacement and cycles were controlled by a
16 National Instruments PXI series real-time controller using a LabView-based graphical user
17 interface, INERTIA, developed by Wineman Technology Inc. During preliminary tests, a
18 Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) closed-loop control method was used to conduct the tests.

19

20 As shown in Figure 4, the total target displacement (radial expansion or contraction of the
21 pneumatic piston) and the displacement increment (y_{sp}) were specified and sent to the PID
22 controller. Then, a voltage command was sent to the piston to adjust the pressure targeting to
23 achieve the first displacement increment and the actual displacement was measured. The error,

1 which is defined as the difference between the command (target displacement increment) and
2 feedback (measured displacement) was calculated and used by the controller to send a new voltage
3 command. Once the error is very small (less than 1 μm), a new displacement increment was
4 targeted and the same process was repeated until the total target displacement was achieved. This
5 is a continuous running closed-loop application (loop rate is 1000 scans a second).

6

7 After performing few preliminary tests, it was observed that the PID system with closed-loop
8 displacement control to simulate expansion and contraction does not function accurately at very
9 small target displacements. To achieve a specific displacement increment, the system tends to set
10 a larger piston pressure, which caused overshooting of the displacement followed by a reduction of
11 the pressure to adjust the displacement. This process occurred several times for each displacement
12 increment resulting in frequent oscillation of the pressure and applying cyclic loading on the soil,
13 which may result in changes of the soil stiffness leading to larger pressure needed to achieve the
14 total target displacement and plastic soil displacement when achieving the total target displacement.
15 This issue will be discussed later in the paper.

16

17 In order to avoid this issue of the PID control system after performing the first few tests, loading
18 control with displacement tracking (LCDT) method was followed to apply expansion and
19 contraction displacements. LCDT was achieved by programing the loading procedure in INERTIA
20 to perform the expansion and contraction displacements and cycles, which will be described later
21 in the experimental procedure.

22

23 **CALIBRATION OF MODIFIED-TBST**

1 The heating or cooling of the fluid circuiting through the aluminum tubes embedded in the concrete
2 plates alters the temperatures of the plates and the pneumatic piston, which changes the readings
3 of the radial displacement sensors between the two shearing plates and the pressure normal to the
4 soil-concrete interface. To account for all these changes, a calibration of the device was performed
5 at temperatures ranging from 2 to 40 °C.

6
7

8 **Effect of Temperature on Displacement Reading**

9 The heating and cooling effects on the reading of the sensors measuring the radial expansion and
10 contraction of the shear head were evaluated by subjecting the shear head to temperature changes.
11 The results of the calibration tests are shown in Figure 5. It was observed that the readings of the
12 radial displacement sensors, used to control and measure the expansion and contraction of the shear
13 head, change due to temperature change only, which is attributed to the expansion and contraction
14 of different parts and materials of the shear head. The total change of the displacement reading
15 divided by the temperature change at the surface of the shearing plate provides a displacement
16 correction factor of the shear head per unit temperature change. Based on six temperature
17 calibration tests, the average displacement correction factor of the shear head was

18 $-1.1\mu\text{m}/^{\circ}\text{C}$.

19
20

21 **Temperature Effects on Horizontal Force**

22 The horizontal (normal) force applied on the soil-concrete interface is controlled by the air pressure
23 in the pneumatic piston. The relationship between the horizontal force and the air pressure in the
24 pneumatic piston was calibrated using a compression machine at different temperatures as shown

1 in Figure 6. Comparing the results at different temperatures, Figure 6 shows that the temperature
2 effect on the measured horizontal force is minimal. It is also worth noting that the air pressure has
3 a linear relation with the horizontal force, except for air pressures smaller than 20 kPa, which
4 correspond to a normal force of 12 N. A coefficient (slope) of 0.81 N/kPa was used to calculate
5 the normal pressure on the soil-concrete interface when the air pressure was larger than 20 kPa.
6 When the air pressure was smaller than 20 kPa, a coefficient of 0.5 N/kPa was utilized.

7

8

9 **MATERIALS AND PREPARATION**

10 **Soil Properties**

11 Soil obtained from a construction site in the Lehigh Valley, Pennsylvania was used to conduct the
12 Modified-TBSTs. Using the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), the soil was classified as
13 sandy silty clay (CL-ML) with 17.5% sand, 54.3% silt, and 25.8% clay. The liquid and plastic
14 limits of the soil were 28% and 22%, respectively, and the solids specific gravity was 2.67.
15 Standard Proctor tests were performed and the maximum dry unit weight and optimum moisture
16 content were 17.4 kN/m³ and 14%, respectively. To perform the Modified-TBSTs inside the soil
17 tank, the soil was compacted in layers to achieve target moisture content of 18% and dry unit weight
18 of 13.8 kN/m³. The measured thermal conductivity of the soil was ~1.1 W/mK and the volumetric
19 heat capacity was ~ 2100 kJ/m³K.

20

21 **Soil Preparation**

22 The soil was mixed at the target moisture content in a concrete mixer. During preliminary tests, it
23 was observed that the average moisture loss during preparation and waiting times was less than
24 0.5%, which was compensated for during soil preparation. As shown in Figure 2, thin polyethylene

1 films placed on the inside surface of the tank were used to reduce the friction between the soil and
2 the tank. Tactilus pressure sheet sensors were also used on the inside surface of the tank to check
3 for boundary effects (Figure 2). The soil was filled in the tank in 7 layers and compacted using a
4 tamper with targeted compaction energy per unit volume of $\sim 54 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}/\text{m}^3$. This consistent
5 procedure was utilized in all experiments and resulted in soil dry unit weight of $13.7 \text{ kN}/\text{m}^3$. During
6 compaction, an aluminum pipe with a diameter of 95 mm was installed in the middle of the tank to
7 create the borehole needed to perform the Thermal-TBSTs. Thermocouples were installed at
8 different locations in the soil as the tank was being filled and the locations of these sensors are
9 shown in Figure 2.

10 After filling the soil in the tank, an overburden pressure (p) of 68.9 kPa was applied on the top
11 surface of the soil for two days to consolidate it (see Figure 2). Then the overburden pressure was
12 released, the aluminum pipe was pulled out of the soil, and the overburden pressure (p) of 68.9 kPa
13 was applied again for another two days. The top lid of soil tank was covered by plastic film to
14 avoid or minimize the loss of the soil moisture during the test.

15

16 **TESTING PROCEDURE**

17 After preparing the soil and consolidating it under vertical overburden pressure (p), the test
18 proceeded using three major stages; the consolidation stage, the temperature and/or displacement
19 stage, and the shearing stage. The details of each of these stages are discussed below.

20

21 **Consolidation Stage**

22 After the soil preparation, the shear head was lowered in the borehole and a constant horizontal (or
23 normal) pressure (σ_h) was applied normal to the soil-concrete interface. The horizontal pressure
24 was increased from 0 kPa to the target pressure value at a rate of 1.55 kPa/s. This constant pressure

1 is called the initial radial consolidation pressure. Initially, the constant pressure was applied for
2 different time intervals to determine the time required for the radial consolidation stage. When
3 subjected to this consolidation pressure, the soil consolidates laterally and the displacement of the
4 shear plates was measured with time. The horizontal pressure vs. radial displacement of the plates
5 of the shear head during the increase of horizontal pressure is presented in Figure 7a, which shows
6 a displacement of 0.71 mm and 0.94 mm for tests with target horizontal pressures of 41.4 and 69.0
7 kPa, respectively. During the consolidation stage, the radial displacement of the plates increased
8 to 0.98 mm and 1.27 mm for consolidation pressure of 41.4 and 69.0 kPa, respectively. Figure 7b
9 presents the radial displacement rates of the shear plates for 24 hours at applied horizontal
10 consolidation pressure (σ_h) of 41.4 and 69.0 kPa. Based on the results from different consolidation
11 time intervals and consolidation pressures, it was noticed that after 12 hours of consolidation, the
12 rate of radial displacement is very small ($< 2 \mu\text{m}/\text{hour}$), which reduces the creep effect of soil during
13 temperature and displacement change stages. Therefore, the initial constant radial consolidation
14 pressure was applied for 12 hours during this stage for other tests. Modified-TBST tests were
15 conducted at radial consolidation pressures of 13.8, 27.6, and 41.4 kPa. It is worth noting that the
16 pressure at the inside wall of the soil tank, which was measured using a Tactilus pressure sheet,
17 showed pressure increase smaller than 0.5 kPa (i.e. $\sim 1\%$ of the pressure applied at borehole) during
18 the tests confirming the minimal effects of the boundary.

19

20 **Applying Temperature Change and Cycles**

21 For tests with temperature change and/or cycles, the shear plates were heated or cooled by
22 circulating a fluid with different temperatures. For heating cycles, one circulating bath was used
23 and the fluid temperature was set to $\sim 8^\circ\text{C}$ higher than the target temperature of the soil-concrete
24 interface (to account the heat loss) measured using a thermocouple on the shearing plate surface.
25 The soil-concrete interface was heated to the target temperature (i.e., reaching 0.5 temperature cycle

1 or $TC = 0.5$ as shown in Figure 8). Then, the circulating bath was stopped, and the other bath started
2 to cool the plates down to room temperature (i.e. reaching 1 heating cycle or $TC = 1$ as shown in
3 Figure 8). For cooling cycles, the fluid temperature was set to ~ 12 °C below the target temperature.
4 The soil-concrete interface was cooled to the target temperature (i.e., reaching 0.5 cooling cycle or
5 $TC = -0.5$ as shown in Figure 8). Then, the circulating bath was stopped and the other bath started
6 to warm up the plates back to the room temperature (i.e. 1 cooling cycle or $TC = -1$). This process
7 could be repeated to apply the target number of heating or cooling cycles. This process was used
8 to better control the interface temperature and to allow for applying several cycles within one
9 testing/working day.

10 Based on the discussion provided in the background section related to the daily running and
11 stoppage times of heat pumps installed in different environments and to allow for applying several
12 cycles within one testing/working day, heating or cooling cycles of 1 hour was targeted in our
13 investigation. Temperature change (ΔT) of 20 °C was used for heating and temperature change of
14 -18 °C was used for cooling. It is worth noting that the target temperature change of 20 °C or 18 °C
15 is higher than the practical case for the daily operation of energy piles which may alter pore pressure
16 of surrounding soil. However, the pore pressure change was measured during tests with
17 temperature cycles (tests with 10 cycles). For the test conditions presented in this paper (silty clay
18 with 17.5% sand, unsaturated condition), the change of pore pressure within 30 min (0.5 cycle) and
19 20 °C temperature change was $\sim 4\%$. The details of the pore pressure measurements will be
20 discussed in a future paper that focuses on effects of temperature and displacement cycles.

21

22 **Applying Radial Displacement Change and Cycles**

23 As previously discussed and will be discussed later, a LCDT displacement control approach was
24 used to address oscillation under PID control. Using the LCDT displacement control approach, the

1 control system adjusts the air pressure of the pneumatic piston to change the normal pressure
2 applied on the soil-concrete interface. The adjusted piston pressure changed the position of the
3 shear plates relative to the surrounding soil [i.e., pushed forward into the soil (simulating pile
4 expansion) or pulled backward (simulating pile contraction)]. As shown in Figure 8, the expansion
5 to a target displacement is defined as 0.5 expansion cycle (radial displacement cycle or RDC = 0.5)
6 and returning the plates to the original position completes a displacement cycle (1 expansion cycle
7 or RDC = 1). Similarly, for contraction cycles the plates contract to a target displacement from the
8 original position (0.5 contraction cycle or RDC = -0.5) followed by returning the plates to their
9 original position, which completes 1 contraction cycle (RDC = -1).

10

11 To calculate the target radial expansion and contraction of energy piles, the pile diameter,
12 temperature difference, and coefficient of thermal expansion (α) of concrete are needed. For
13 example, an energy pile with 0.6 m diameter, $\alpha = 10^{-6} \mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$ subjected to 20 °C temperature changes
14 is expected to expand and contract by 120 μm , which was used in our tests. This target displacement
15 can be achieved using the PID control or the LCDDT control systems. The performance of the device
16 using both of these systems will be compared in the results section. It is worth noting that
17 confinement from surrounding soil may affect the radial strain of energy piles. For example,
18 Mimouni and Laloui (2015), based on results of field test, concluded that radial strain was partially
19 restrained, while Wang et al. (2015), who performed an O-cell test on an energy pile, reported that
20 the pile expanded freely in the radial direction. During the tests presented in this paper, a free radial
21 expansion was assumed.

22

23 **Shearing Stage**

1 After temperature and/or radial displacement change/cycles were applied, the shear head was pulled
2 upward shearing the soil-concrete interface and the applied pull out force and the vertical
3 displacement were measured (i.e., producing shear stress vs. vertical displacement curves or t-z
4 curves). Shearing was applied at a constant rate of 0.05 mm/s. During the shearing stage, control
5 in the radial direction can use displacement control (DC) or load control (LC). If displacement
6 control is used, the radial displacement of the concrete plates is maintained constant by adjusting
7 the horizontal pressure. If load control is used, the horizontal pressure at the soil-concrete interface
8 is maintained constant. The difference between the two control procedures during the shearing
9 stage will be discussed later. It is important to note that the tests without temperature change were
10 conducted first to avoid any temperature effects on surrounding soil. Furthermore, the shear head
11 was rotated between tests so each position was only sheared once.

12

13 **PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND ANALYSIS**

14 **PID vs. LCDT Control**

15 To evaluate the performance of the PID control, the radial displacement and the corresponding
16 horizontal pressure at the interface for trial tests with 10.5 expansion cycles (RDC = 10.5, TC = 0)
17 are presented in Figure 9a. The tests were performed at room temperature using both PID closed-
18 loop control and LCDT methods. At the beginning of the expansion cycles (Point A in Figure 9a),
19 the initial radial consolidation pressure was 41.4 kPa. At the end of first half expansion cycle (RDC
20 = 0.5, Points B and B' in Figure 9a) with target expansion of 120 μm , the horizontal pressure
21 increased from 41.4 kPa to 49.7 kPa for the LCDT method and to 63.0 kPa for the PID control
22 method. When the plates returned to the initial position at 1 expansion cycle (RDC = 1, Points C
23 and C' in Figure 9a), the horizontal pressure was 16.0 kPa for LCDT and 8.5 kPa for PID control.
24 The horizontal pressure-displacement response of these two control methods also have a significant
25 difference during the following expansion cycles (Figure 9a). Using the LCDT method, the

1 horizontal pressure at 10 and 10.5 expansion cycles (Points D and E in Figure 9a) were 11.4 and
2 40.4 kPa, respectively. However, using the PID control, the horizontal pressure at 10 and 10.5
3 expansion cycles (Points D' and E' in Figure 9a) were 4.4 and 54.3 kPa, respectively. As discussed
4 before, the differences between the two systems could be attributed to the frequent oscillation of
5 pressure (applying cyclic loading on the soil), which resulted in changes of the soil stiffness leading
6 to larger pressures and plastic soil deformations. This pressure oscillation of the PID control is
7 clearly shown in Figure 9b, which focus on the collected data for the first 60 seconds of the control
8 systems. While the pressure with LCDT method was stable compared to that with PID control.
9 The horizontal pressure increased from 41.4 to 44.4 kPa in 60 seconds. The corresponding
10 expansion of the plates increased around 6 μ m in the first 60 second using LCDT method compared
11 to 4 μ m in the test with PID closed-loop displacement control.

12

13 **Effect of Radial Consolidation Time Interval**

14 The effect of radial consolidation time on the shear stress-vertical displacement response of the
15 soil-concrete interface (i.e., t-z curves) was investigated. Figure 10 shows the t-z curves of the soil-
16 concrete interface with radial consolidation times of 15 minutes, 1 hour and 12 hours for an initial
17 consolidation pressure of 41.4 kPa. Peak strengths of 26.9, 27.6, and 26.7 kPa were measured at
18 consolidation times of 15 minutes, 1 hour and 12 hours, respectively. Figure 10 shows that the
19 effect of consolidation time on interface shear strength was not significant (only 3.3% maximum
20 difference). However, the values of the stiffness of the soil-concrete interface at 50% of the peak
21 shear strength (G_{50}) were also compared. The stiffness (G_{50}) was calculated using by Equation 1

$$22 \quad G_{50} = \frac{\tau_{50}}{d_{50}} \quad (1)$$

1 where τ_{50} is 50% of the shear strength, and d_{50} is the vertical displacement of the shear plates
2 corresponding to τ_{50} .

3 The G_{50} of soil-concrete interface with consolidation time of 15 min, 1 hour, and 12 hours were
4 182.2, 194.3, and 212.2 kPa/mm, which shows a maximum difference of ~16%. Based on these
5 results, and those shown in Figure 7, a radial consolidation time of 12 hours was used in all other
6 tests.

7

8 **Load Control vs. Displacement Control during Shearing Stage**

9 Figure 11 shows the measured t-z curves of tests subjected to initial consolidation pressures of 13.8,
10 27.6, and 41.4 kPa without temperature or displacement cycles. After finishing the radial
11 consolidation stage, the control in the radial direction was changed to a displacement control (DC)
12 keeping the plates at the same radial (horizontal) distance as that at the end of radial consolidation,
13 while the other set of tests was performed by keeping the horizontal pressure constant using load
14 control (LC). In both sets of tests, the shearing was performed using a constant rate of displacement
15 of 0.05 mm/s. Figure 11 illustrates that the measured t-z curves with DC show a softening response
16 after achieving the peak strength. Furthermore, the peak and ultimate shear strength of the soil-
17 concrete interface for tests performed with LC was higher than those performed with DC. This
18 difference could be attributed to the reduction of the horizontal pressure when the system was trying
19 to keep the same radial distance between the two plates in DC. For example, for the tests with
20 initial radial consolidation pressure of 27.6 kPa, the horizontal pressure decreased significantly
21 from 27.6 kPa to 14.7 kPa during shearing when the radial distance between the plates was kept
22 constant during shearing. During shearing, the plates could rotate very slightly when subjected to
23 pull out force changing the radial displacement readings triggering a change of the horizontal
24 pressure. This very small rotation of the plates may cause the tilt of a horizontal displacement

1 sensor or the tip of the displacement sensor to slide of the back of the shearing plate. Because of
2 the issues and to allow for comparing the responses of tests at different conditions, the LC is
3 recommended and was used for future tests.

4

5 **Preliminary Test Results**

6 After finalizing the testing procedure and calibration based on the tests discussed before, a series
7 of Modified-TBSTs were performed with radial consolidation pressure of 41.4 kPa. A reference
8 test was conducted without temperature or displacement cycles (RDC = 0, TC = 0). The strength
9 of the shear stress-vertical displacement (t-z curve) for this reference test was 35.8 kPa. Figure 12
10 shows the t-z curves after 0.5 heating cycle (RDC = 0, TC = 0.5), 0.5 expansion cycle (RDC = 0.5,
11 TC = 0), and the combination of 0.5 expansion and 0.5 heating cycles (RDC = 0.5 and TC = 0.5).
12 When compared to the reference test, the interface strength decreased by 9% for the test with RDC
13 = 0 and TC = 0.5. According to Murphy and McCartney (2014), this difference could be attributed
14 to undrained heating which may increase thermally-induced pore pressures resulting in thermal
15 softening. However, for the test conditions presented in this paper (silty clay with 17.5% sand,
16 unsaturated condition), the change of pore pressure within 30 min (0.5 cycle) and 20 °C temperature
17 change was ~4%. For the test with half cycle heating and expansion (RDC = 0.5, TC = 0.5), the
18 interface strength was 40.6 kPa (13.4% increase) and it was 43.6 kPa (21.8% increase) for the test
19 with half cycle expansion (RDC = 0.5, TC = 0). During expansion, the concrete plates expand
20 toward the soil and the horizontal pressure at the interface increases. For the test with half
21 expansion cycle, the horizontal pressure increased from 41.4 kPa to 49.5 kPa. For the test with half
22 heating and expansion cycle, the horizontal pressure increased to 46.7 kPa. The difference between
23 the two radial pressures during these two tests could be attributed to the effects of temperature on
24 soil properties (stiffness), which could be as high as 30% according to the stress relaxation tests
25 performed by Murayama (1969) for a saturated clay subjected to temperature change. The decrease

1 of stiffness with increasing temperature was also observed by Zhou and Ng (2015) for unsaturated
2 fine soils.

3

4 Figure 12 also show the t-z curves after 0.5 cooling cycle (RDC = 0, TC = -0.5), 0.5 contraction
5 cycle (RDC = -0.5, TC = 0), and the combination of 0.5 contraction and 0.5 cooling cycles (RDC
6 = -0.5 and TC = -0.5). For the test with RDC = 0 and TC = -0.5, the interface strength was 38.4
7 kPa (increased by 7% compared to the reference test). The interface shear strength was 9.2 kPa for
8 the test with half cycle contraction (RDC = -0.5, TC = 0), which decreased by 74% when compared
9 to the reference tests due to the reduction of horizontal pressure at the interface. For the test with
10 RDC = -0.5 and TC = -0.5, the shear strength was 8.8 kPa. Based on the results for the test
11 conditions (unsaturated cohesive soil), the effect of expansion and contraction on the interface shear
12 strength is significantly larger than that of temperature change only.

13

14 **SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS**

15 This paper presents a detailed description of a new fully-automated Modified-TBST device. To
16 simulate the effects of intermittent operation of the heat pump on soil-foundation interaction of
17 energy piles, this device is capable of combining the effects of temperature change and cycles with
18 radial expansion/contraction (displacement) cycles, or separating those effects. Based on the
19 preliminary tests and calibration, LCDD method was proposed for simulating the expansion and
20 contraction displacements and cycles of energy piles. The LCDD method is based on the load
21 control with stable output and it eliminates the oscillation of horizontal pressure, which was
22 observed with the PID closed-loop displacement control. The tests performed at different radial
23 consolidation time intervals showed small difference in interface strength. However, adequate
24 radial consolidation time is required to minimize the soil creep effect on simulated expansion and

1 contraction cycles. Therefore, a radial consolidation time of 12 hours is recommended to perform
2 the Modified-TBST. During the shearing stage, both displacement control (DC) and load control
3 (LC) methods were used to control the system in the radial direction. The LC method showed
4 better results allowing for comparing different tests and evaluating the effects of temperature and
5 displacement changes and cycles. Based on the preliminary results of t-z curves, thermal softening
6 was observed in the test with 0.5 temperature cycle. Although the temperature change (20 °C) does
7 not reflect the daily temperature change in energy piles, the maximum effect of temperature only
8 (with no cycles) on the interface shear strength was 9% for the tested soil conditions. However, the
9 effects of expansion and contraction were significant (up to 74%). Compared to the reference test,
10 the test with half cycle of heating and expansion (RDC = 0.5, TC = 0.5) showed a 13.4% increase,
11 while for the test with half cycle expansion (RDC = 0.5, TC = 0), the strength increased by 21.8%.
12 The difference between these two tests could be attributed to the effect of temperature on soil
13 properties. For the tests with half contraction cycle (RDC = -0.5, TC = 0) and the test with half
14 cycle of cooling and contraction (RDC = -0.5, TC = -0.5), the interface shear strength experienced
15 more than 70% reduction due to the decrease of horizontal pressure. The measured changes
16 presented in this paper are consistent with those reported by Wang et al. (2015) and Suryatriyastuti
17 et al. (2012). Future tests will focus on evaluating the effects of temperature cycles simulating the
18 intermittent operation of heat pumps connected to energy piles.

19

20 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

21 This work was made possible by an NPRP 7-725-2-270 grant from the Qatar National Research
22 Fund (a member of Qatar Foundation). The statements made herein are solely the responsibility of
23 the authors.

24

1 **REFERENCES**

- 2 Abdelaziz, S. L., Olgun, C. G., and Martin II, J. R., 2011, "Design and Operational Considerations
3 of Geothermal Energy Piles," *Proceedings of GeoFrontiers 2011*, Dallas, Texas, CD-ROM.
- 4 AbdelSalam, S. S., Suleiman, M. T., and Sritharan, S., 2012, "Enhanced Load-transfer Analysis
5 for Friction Piles using a Modified Borehole Shear Test," *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, Vol.
6 35, No. 6, pp. 1–11.
- 7 Adam, D., Markiewicz, R., 2009, "Energy from Earth-coupled Structures, Foundations, Tunnels
8 and Sewers," *Géotechnique*, Vol. 59, No. 3, 229–236.
- 9 Akrouch, G., Sanchez, M., and Briaud, J. L., 2013, "Energy Piles for Heating and Cooling
10 Purposes," *Proceedings of the 5th International Young Geotechnical Engineers' Congerence*,
11 edited by Cui, Y.-J., Emeriault, F., Cuir, F., Ghabezloo, S., Pereira, J.-M., Reboul, M., Ravel,
12 H., Tang, A.M. Millpress, pp. 161–164.
- 13 Amatya, B.L., Soga, K., Bourne-Webb, P.J., Amis, T., and Laloui, L., 2012, "Thermo-mechanical
14 Behaviour of Energy Piles," *Géotechnique*, Vol. 62, No. 6, pp. 503–519.
- 15 Amis, T., 2011, "Energy Foundation In the UK," Presentation to Swiss Federal Institute of
16 Technology Lausanne, EPFL, Switzerland. Retrieved from Internet Archive website:
17 http://web.archive.org/web/20170217214106/http://www.gshp.org.uk/GroundSourceLive2011/TonyAmis_Piles_gsl.pdf (accessed Dec 15, 2016).
- 18
- 19 Batini, N., Rotta Loria, A. F., Conti, P., Testi, D., Grassi, W., Laloui, L. 2015, "Energy and
20 Geotechnical Behaviour of Energy Piles for Different Design Solutions," *Computers and*
21 *Geotechnics*, Vol. 86, No. 1, pp. 199–213.
- 22 Bourne-Webb, P. J., Amatya, B., Soga, K., Amis, T., Davidson, C. and Payne, P., 2009, "Energy
23 Pile Test at Lambeth College, London: Geotechnical and Thermodynamic Aspects of Pile
24 Response to Heat Cycles," *Géotechnique*, Vol. 59, No. 3, pp. 237–248.

- 1 Bourne-Webb, P., 2013, "Observed Response of Energy Geostructures," in: Energy Geo-Structures,
2 Laloui, L. and Di Donna, A. (Ed.), p. 29, *ISTE - John Wiley & Sons*, London, (2013).
- 3 Brandl, H., 2006, "Energy Foundations and Other Geothermal Ground Structures," *Géotechnique*,
4 Vol. 56, No. 2, pp. 81–122.
- 5 Burghignoli, A., Desideri, A., and Miliziano, S., 2000, "A Laboratory Study on the
6 Thermomechanical Behaviour of Clayey Soils," *Can. Geotech. J.*, Vol. 37, No. 4, pp. 764–
7 780.
- 8 Campanella, R. G. and Mitchell, J. K., 1968, "Influence of Temperature Variations on Soil
9 Behavior," *Journal of Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering*, ASCE 94 (SM3), pp.
10 709–734.
- 11 Cekerevac, C., and Laloui, L., 2004, "Experimental Study of Thermal Effects on the Mechanical
12 Behaviour of a Clay," *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in*
13 *Geomechanics*, Vol. 28, No. 3, pp. 209–228.
- 14 Demartinencourt, J. P., and Bauer, G. E., 1983, "The Modified Borehole Shear Device,"
15 *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 24–29.
- 16 Di Donna, A., Ferrari, A., and Laloui, L., 2015, "Experimental Investigations of the Soil–concrete
17 Interface: Physical Mechanisms, Cyclic Mobilization, and Behaviour at Different
18 Temperatures," *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, Vol. 53, No. 4, pp. 659–672.
- 19 Gabrielsson, A., Bergdahl, U., and Moritz, L., 2000, "Thermal Energy Storage in Soils at
20 Temperatures Reaching 90 degrees C," *J. Solar Energy Eng.–Trans. ASME*, Vol. 122, No. 1,
21 pp. 3–8.
- 22 Gao, J., Zhang, X., Liu, J., Li, K., and Yang, J. 2008, "Numerical and Experimental Assessment of
23 Thermal Performance of Vertical Energy Piles: An application," *Applied Energy*, Vol. 5, No.
24 10, pp. 901–910.

- 1 Hamada, Y., Saitoh, H., Nakamura, M., Kubota, H., and Ochifuji, K. 2007, "Field performance of
2 an energy pile system for space heating," *Energy and Buildings*, Vol. 39, No. 5, pp.517–524.
- 3 Handy, R. L., 1986, "Borehole Shear Test and Slope Stability," *Proceeding: The ASCE Specialty*
4 *Conference on In-Situ tests: Use of In-Situ Tests in Geotechnical Engineering*, Blacksburg,
5 Virginia, pp. 161–175.
- 6 Handy, R. L., and Fox, N. S., 1967, "A Soil Borehole Direct Shear Test Device," *Highway Research*
7 *News, Transportation Research Record*, Vol. 27, pp. 42–51.
- 8 Houston, S. L., Houston, W. N., and Williams, N. D., 1985, "Thermo-mechanical Behavior of
9 Seafloor Sediments," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering ASCE*, Vol. 111, No. 12, pp. 1249–
10 1263.
- 11 Kuntiwattanakul, P., Towhata, I., Ohishi, K., and Seko, I., 1995, "Temperature Effects on
12 Undrained Shear Characteristics of Clay," *Soils and Foundation*, Vol. 35, No.1, pp. 147–162.
- 13 Laguros, J. G., 1969, "Effect of Temperature on Some Engineering Properties of Clay Soils,"
14 *Highway Research Board Special Report*, pp. 186–193.
- 15 Laloui, L., Nuth, M., and Vulliet, L., 2006, "Experimental and Numerical Investigations of the
16 Behavior of a Heat Exchanger Pile," *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical*
17 *Methods in Geomechanics*, Vol. 30, No. 8, pp. 763–781.
- 18 Laloui., L., Di Donna, A. 2013. *Energy Geostructures: Innovation in Underground Engineering*.
19 August 2013, Wiley-ISTE.
- 20 Loveridge, F. A., Powrie, W., Amis, T., Wischy, M. and Kiauk, J., 2016, "Long Term Monitoring
21 of CFA Energy Pile Schemes in the UK," in: Wuttke, F, Bauer, S and Sanchez, M, (eds.)
22 *Energy Geotechnics. 1st International Conference on Energy Geotechnics (ICEGT 2016)*, 29-
23 31 Aug 2016, Keil, Germany. CRC Press, pp. 585-592.

- 1 Lutenegger, A. J., and Powell, J. J. M., 2008, "Borehole Shear Tests in Stiff London and Gault
2 Clay," *Proceedings of the 3rd International Symposium on Site Characterization*, Taipei,
3 Taiwan, April 1–4, pp. 719–723.
- 4 Lutenegger, A. J., and Tierney, K. F., 1986, "Pore Pressure Effects in Borehole Shear Testing,"
5 *Proceeding: The ASCE Specialty Conference on In-Situ tests: Use of In-Situ Tests in*
6 *Geotechnical Engineering*, Blacksburg, Virginia, pp. 752–764.
- 7 Lutenegger, A. J., Renames, B. D., and Handy, R. L., 1978, "Borehole Shear Test for Stiff soil,"
8 *Journal of the Geotechnical Engineering Division*, Vo. 104, No. 11, pp. 1403–1407.
- 9 Mašín, D., and Khalili, N., 2014, "A Thermo-mechanical Model for Variably Saturated Soils Based
10 on Hypoplasticity," *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in*
11 *Geomechanics*, Vol. 36, No. 12, pp.1461–1485.
- 12 McCartney, J. S., and Murphy, K. D., 2012, "Strain Distributions in Full-Scale Energy
13 Foundations," *Deep Foundation Institute Journal*, Vol. 6, No. 2, pp. 28–38.
- 14 Mimouni, T., and Laloui, L., 2014, "Behaviour of a Group of Energy Piles," *Canadian*
15 *Geotechnical Journal*, Vol. 52, No. 12, pp. 1913–1929.
- 16 Montagud, C., Corberan, J. M., Montero, A., and Urchueguia, J. F., 2011, "Analysis of the Energy
17 Performance of a Ground Source Heat Pump System After Five Years of Operation," *Energy*
18 *and Buildings*, Vol. 43, pp. 3618–3626.
- 19 Murayama, S., 1969, "Effects of Temperature on Elasticity of Clays," *Highway Research Board*,
20 *Special Report 103, Conference on Effects of Temperature and Heat on Engineering*
21 *Behaviour of Soils*. Sponsored by The Committee on Physico-Chemical Phenomena in Soils.
22 pp. 194-203.
- 23 Murphy, K., and McCartney, J., 2014, "Thermal Borehole Shear Device," *Geotechnical Testing*
24 *Journal*, Vol. 37, No. 6, pp. 1–16.

- 1 Murphy, K., and McCartney, J., 2015, "Seasonal Response of Energy Foundations During Building
2 Operation," *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, Vol. 33, No. 2, pp. 343–356.
- 3 Noble, C. A., and Demirel, T., 1969, "Effect of Temperature on Strength Behavior of Cohesive
4 Soil," *Highway Research Board Special Report*, pp. 204–219.
- 5 Olgun, C. G., Ozudogru, T. Y., and Arson, C. F., 2014, "Thermo–mechanical Radial Expansion
6 of Heat Exchanger Piles and Possible Effects on Contact Pressures at Pile–soil Interface,"
7 *Géotechnique Letters*, Vol. 4, No. 3, pp. 170–178.
- 8 Ooka, R., Sekine, K., Mutsumi, Y., Yoshiro, S., and SuckHo, H., 2007, "Development of a Ground
9 Source Heat Pump System with Ground Heat Exchanger Utilizing the Cast–in Place Concrete
10 Pile Foundations of a Building," *2007 Winter Meeting of the American Society of Heating,
11 Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers*. Dallas, TX, United states. Jan 27–31, 2007.
- 12 Preene, M., and Powrie, W., 2009, "Ground Energy Systems: From Analysis to Geotechnical
13 Design," *Géotechnique*, Vol. 59, No. 3, pp. 287–290.
- 14 Saggi, R. and Chakraborty, T., "Cyclic Thermo-Mechanical Analysis of Energy Piles in Sand,"
15 *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, Vol. 33, No. 2, pp. 321–342.
- 16 Shang, Y., Li. S., and Li, H., 2011, "Analysis of Geo-temperature Recovery under Intermittent
17 Operation of Ground-source Heat Pump," *Energy and Buildings*, Vol. 43, No. 4, pp. 935–943.
- 18 Suleiman, M. AbdelSalam, S., and Sritharan, S., 2011, "Improving Prediction of the Load–
19 Displacement Response of Axially Loaded Friction Piles," *Proceedings of Geo–Frontiers
20 2011, Advances in Geotechnical Engineering, ASCE*, pp. 36–45.
- 21 Suleiman, M. T., and Xiao, S., 2014, "Soil–Pile Interaction of Geothermal Deep Foundations,"
22 *Proceedings of the 27th Central Pennsylvania Geotechnical Conference*, Hershey, PA on
23 April 23–25, 2014.

- 1 Suryatriyastuti, M. E., Mroueha, H., and Burlonb, S., 2012, "Understanding the Temperature–
2 induced Mechanical Behaviour of Energy Pile Foundations," *Renewable and Sustainable*
3 *Energy Reviews*, Vol. 16, No. 5, pp. 3344–3354.
- 4 Wang, B., Bouazza, A., Singh, R., Haberfield, C., Barry–Macaulay, D., and Baycan, S., 2014,
5 "Posttemperature Effects on Shaft Capacity of a Full–scale Geothermal Energy Pile," *Journal*
6 *of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, Vol. 141, No. 4, pp. 04014125: 1–12.
- 7 Wood, C. J., Liu, H., and Riffat, S. B., 2009, "Use of Energy Piles in a Residential Building, and
8 Effects on Ground Temperature and Heat Pump Efficiency," *Géotechnique*, Vol. 59, No. 3,
9 pp. 287–290.
- 10 Xiao, S., Suleiman, M. T., Elzeiny. R., Xie, H., and Al-Khawaja, M. J., 2017, "Soil-concrete
11 Interface Properties Subjected to Cyclic Thermal Loading Using Direct Shear Test,"
12 *Geotechnical Frontiers 2017*, Orlando, Florida, March 12-15, 2017.
- 13 Xiao, S., Suleiman, M. T., and McCartney, J. S., 2014, "Shear Behavior of Silty Soil and Soil-
14 Structure Interface under Thermal Loading," *2014 GeoCongress, Geo-Characterization and*
15 *Modeling for Sustainability*. Atlanta, Georgia, February 23–26, 2014.
- 16 Yavari, N., Tang, A. H., Pereira, J., and Hassen, G., 2016, "Effect of Temperature on the Shear
17 Strength of Soils and the Soil–structure Interface," *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, Vol. 53,
18 No. 7, pp. 1–9.
- 19 Zhou, C., and Ng. C. W. W., 2015, "Effects of Temperature and Suction on the Stiffness of
20 Unsaturated Soil under Cyclic Loads," *International Symposium on Energy Geotechnics*,
21 Barcelona, Spain, 2-4 June 2015.

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3 **Figure 1. Pile subjected to vertical loading showing horizontal stresses normal to the soil-**
4 **pile interface, (a) Conventional pile; (b) radial expansion of energy pile during heating; and**
5 **(c) radial contraction of energy pile during cooling**

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Figure 2: Configuration of the Modified-TBST system

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Figure 3. Configuration of concrete plates and shear head: (a) side view of the shear head; (b) cross section of concrete plate; (c) left plate and heat exchange pipe; (d) right plate and heat exchange pipe; (e) photo of the shear head with concrete plates.

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Figure 4. Block diagram of PID control system

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Figure 5. Calibration of the change of radial displacement sensor readings due to temperature effects on the shear head

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Figure 6. Relationship between the horizontal (normal) force of pneumatic piston and air pressure at different temperatures

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(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Radial displacement at consolidation pressure of 41.4 and 69.0 kPa during consolidation stage, (a) horizontal pressure vs. radial displacement; (b) change of radial displacement as a function of time

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Figure 8. Temperature and displacement cycles of the test device

6 **Figure 9. Comparison of PID control and LCDT, (a) horizontal pressure vs. displacement**
 7 **for expansion cycles; (b) horizontal pressure and radial displacement at the beginning of**
 8 **PID control and LCDT**

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Figure 10. t-z curves of soil-concrete interface at different consolidation times

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Figure 11. Comparison of t-z curves with load control and displacement control in radial direction during shearing

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Figure 12. t-z curves at initial consolidation pressure of 41.4 kPa